

Effect of transient coupled hydro-mechanical response on the longitudinal displacement profile of deep tunnels in saturated ground

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Abstract

An advancing tunnel in deep saturated ground induces coupled interactions between transient fluid flow and deformation that affect the hydro-mechanical (H-M) response of the ground surrounding the excavation. The use of the convergence-confinement method (CCM) to simplify this three-dimensional (3-D) coupled problem into a 2-D plane strain model must then account for this transient coupling effect. Similarly, the induced radial displacement of the tunnel, commonly represented as the longitudinal displacement profile (LDP), will also be influenced by this time-dependent coupled interaction. This study investigates the effect of the transient H-M interaction on the practical implementation of the CCM and the LDP of an advancing tunnel in deep saturated ground. The tunnel is represented by a 2-D axisymmetric coupled H-M model that is built into the computer program Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua (FLAC) and is subjected to an isotropic in situ stress field. First, the study analyzes the induced pore pressure and deformation behavior during the excavation and standstill periods. Second, to account for the transient coupling effect, this study proposes: (1) nonlinear unloading factors for estimating excavation-induced pore pressure changes in CCM and (2) new LDP equations for predicting transient radial displacements along the axis of the tunnel. The resulting relationships from the two propositions are normalized, and thus, they should be applicable to other tunnel depths as well.

Keywords

Hydro-mechanical interaction; Transient coupling effect; Deep advancing tunnel; Convergence-confinement method; Nonlinear unloading factor; Longitudinal displacement profile

1. Introduction

In deep saturated ground, tunnel advance induces a transient coupled interaction between fluid flow and deformation that affects the hydro-mechanical (H-M) response of the ground surrounding the excavation. Due to this transient coupling effect, the excavation will generate instantaneous pore pressure buildup when the ground is being excavated; this is called undrained loading. With time, this excess pore pressure will dissipate as the ground is consolidating; this is called drained consolidation. Even after excavation reaches the final tunnel face, consolidation will continue during the standstill period until the steady-state pore pressure distribution is reached (Ramoni and Anagnostou, 2011).

Convergence-confinement method (CCM) is a standard approach for estimating tunnel wall displacement and tunnel support pressure for deep circular tunnels subjected to an isotropic stress field. A longitudinal displacement profile (LDP) will then relate the wall displacement to the actual location along the tunnel axis. Thus, by integrating CCM and LDP, the amount of the required support pressure and the appropriate time for the support installation as functions to the distance to tunnel face can be determined (Vlachopoulos and Diederichs, 2014, 2009). However, unlike tunneling in dry ground, the estimation of wall displacement and support pressure for tunneling in saturated ground is a non-trivial task due to the transient coupling effect induced by the consolidating ground.

Thus, the purpose of this study is to investigate how the transient coupling effect will influence the practical implementation of CCM and LDP to an advancing tunnel in deep saturated ground. The following subsections will further explain the rationale for considering the transient coupling effect on the current formulations of CCM and LDP.

1.1. Convergence-confinement method

The convergence-confinement method (CCM) has been widely used to simplify the complex three-dimensional (3-D) loading conditions of an advancing tunnel into an equivalent 2-D plane strain model. According to Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst (2000):

“The Convergence-Confinement method is a procedure that allows the load imposed on a support installed behind the face of a tunnel to be estimated. When a section of support is

installed in the immediate vicinity of the tunnel face, it does not carry the full load to which it will be subjected eventually. A part of the load that is redistributed around the excavation is carried by the face itself. As the tunnel and face advance (i.e., away from the installed support), this face effect decreases and the support must carry a greater proportion of the load that the face had carried earlier. When the face has moved well away from the support in question, it carries effectively, the full design load. (p. 188).”

To further describe the above concept of the CCM, Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst (2000) illustrated the sequence of the tunnel advance as equivalently shown in Fig. 1. The sequence starts at time t_0 (Fig. 1a) in which the liner has been installed at section A–A, located at a distance L from the face and the ground has converged radially by the amount of u_r^0 . At this initial time t_0 , the liner carries no load, i.e., $p_s = p_s^0$. As the tunnel advances (Fig. 1b), the support at section A–A is now located at a distance L_t from the face and carries the partial load p_s^t that the face had been carrying previously. At this instant t , the ground deforms by the amount of u_r^t . Once the tunnel has advanced far enough from section A–A (Fig. 1c), spanning a distance L_F from the face, the face effect disappears. The support will carry the full excavation load p_s^F and the ground will converge to its maximum radial displacement u_r^{max} .

The sequence of tunnel advance in Fig. 1 reveals the canonical problem in the design of tunnel support: predicting the amount of the excavation load that the tunnel support must carry before the support is installed. If full excavation load is assumed to occur, the support will carry overpredicted loads. If complete relaxation at the tunnel boundary is assumed to occur, the support will carry no loads. In reality, partial relaxation takes place. However, it is difficult to quantify the degree of relaxation because it depends on the distance behind the face at which the support is installed. The difficulty even increases considerably when shotcrete is used as tunnel support because the progressive hardening of the shotcrete makes the problem time-dependent (Graziani et al., 2005).

For tunneling in saturated ground, to simulate ground relaxation due to tunnel advancement, the CCM applies the equivalent excavation force $\sigma(t)$ and excavation pore pressures $\bar{p}(t)$ on the tunnel boundary as

$$\sigma(t) = (1 - \lambda(t)) \sigma_o \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{p}(t) = (1 - \alpha(t)) p_o \quad (2)$$

where σ_o and p_o are the in situ stress and pore pressure, respectively, and $\lambda(t)$ and $\alpha(t)$ are the unloading factors (ranging from 0 to 1) for excavation force and excavation pore pressure, respectively. The unloading factors are functions of time from the start of excavation to the total relaxation.

Recent research has shown that undrained and drained loading will create non-monotonic pore pressure increase during tunnel excavation (Prasetyo and Gutierrez, 2016a, 2016b). Yet, for tunneling in saturated ground, the current practice of CCM still uses a linear function of pore pressure vs. excavation time for $\alpha(t)$ as demonstrated by Callari (2004), and Callari and Casini (2005). This means that the current practice assumes a linear dissipation of pore pressure with time (commonly converted as a function of distance to tunnel face), neglecting the transient coupling effect between fluid flow and deformation induced by the excavation (Fig. 2). In other words, the current practice may apply improper equivalent pore pressure on the tunnel boundary, which may result in incorrect 3-D representation of the induced H-M response of the advancing tunnel. Thus, the first question addressed in this paper is: Will the transient coupling effect modify the linearity of the unloading factors for excavation pore pressure in CCM?

1.2. Longitudinal displacement profile

Due to the transient generation and dissipation of pore pressure, the corresponding tunnel deformation will also be time-dependent. This deformation is commonly represented by the so-called longitudinal displacement profile or LDP, representing the radial displacements of the tunnel wall along the longitudinal axis of the tunnel (Fig. 3). For tunneling in dry ground, researchers have developed equations to estimate the normalized LDP or $u_r/u_{r,max}$ for a deep circular tunnel located in a hydrostatic stress field. Some of the most well-known LDP equations are summarized below. In the following equations, u_r is the radial displacement of the tunnel wall, $u_{r,max}$ is the maximum radial displacement of the tunnel wall, x is the distance to tunnel face, and D is the tunnel diameter.

Panet and Guenot (1982) and Panet (1993) presented the following expression for creating LDP in the region behind the face ($x/D \geq 0$).

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = 0.28 + 0.72 \left(1 - \left(\frac{0.84}{0.84 + 2x/D} \right)^2 \right) \quad (3)$$

Corbetta et al. (1991) suggested a similar form of LDP equation for the same region behind the face ($x/D \geq 0$).

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = 0.29 + 0.71 \left[1 - \exp(-1.5(2x/D))^{0.7} \right] \quad (4)$$

Later, Panet (1995) revised the earlier version in Eq. (3) and suggested the following relationship.

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = 0.25 + 0.75 \left(1 - \left(\frac{0.75}{0.75 + 2x/D} \right)^2 \right) \quad (5)$$

For the first time, Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst (2000) proposed the complete form of the LDP curve covering the region ahead of ($x/D < 0$) and behind the tunnel face ($x/D \geq 0$).

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = \left(1 + \exp \left(1 - \frac{2x/D}{1.10} \right) \right)^{-1.7} \quad (6)$$

Unlu and Gercek (2003), having considered the effect of Poisson's ratio ν , expressed the radial displacement located ahead of ($x/D < 0$) and behind the tunnel face ($x/D \geq 0$) using the following equations, respectively.

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = U_o + A_a \left(1 - \exp(-B_a 2x/D) \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = U_o + A_b \left(1 - \left(\frac{B_b}{B_b + 2x/D} \right)^2 \right) \quad (8)$$

where $U_o = 0.22\nu + 0.19$, $A_a = -0.22\nu - 0.19$, $B_a = 0.73\nu + 0.81$, $A_b = -0.22\nu + 0.81$, $B_b = 0.39\nu + 0.65$.

Lastly, having considered the influence of maximum plastic radius R_p , Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) expressed the radial displacement located ahead of ($X^* \leq 0$) and behind the tunnel face ($X^* \geq 0$) using the following equations, respectively.

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = u_0^* \exp(X^*) \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = 1 - (1 - u_0^*) \exp\left(-\frac{3X^*}{2R^*}\right) \quad (10)$$

where $u_0^* = \exp(-0.15R^*)/3$, $R^* = R_p/R$, R is the tunnel radius, and $X^* = x/R$.

For tunneling in saturated ground, tunnel displacement is not only caused by the change of effective stresses due to the excavation but also by the seepage forces as the water flows towards the tunnel (Bobet, 2003; Lee et al., 2003; Lee and Nam, 2004, 2001). Nam and Bobet (2007) conducted a pioneering investigation of this groundwater effect on the radial displacement of a deep circular tunnel in saturated ground. The result of the study was a set of LDP equations that accounts for the ratio of pore pressure to effective stress.

The LDP equations of Nam and Bobet (2007) expresses the radial displacement located ahead of ($x/D < 0$) and behind the tunnel face ($x/D \geq 0$) using the following equations, respectively.

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = 0.28 \exp\left(2.11 \frac{x}{D}\right) + 0.2 \exp\left(\frac{x}{5D}\right) \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{p_o}{\sigma'_{vo}}\right)\right) \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = \frac{u_{ro}}{u_{r,max}} + \left(1 - \frac{u_{ro}}{u_{r,max}}\right) \left(1 - \left(\frac{0.75}{0.75 + x/D}\right)^2\right) \quad (12)$$

where p_o is the initial pore pressure and σ'_{vo} is the initial effective vertical stress. The equations matched the radial displacements of an unlined circular tunnel simulated under a hydrostatic in situ stress field (Fig. 4).

Despite its capability in matching the simulation results, the LDP equations from Nam and Bobet (2007) was developed through a series of uncoupled simulations under the steady-state pore pressure conditions. This means that the final tunnel face is reached in one excavation step, as opposed to a step-wise coupled manner, and is geomechanically equilibrated under the steady-

state pore pressure distribution instead of under the transient one. For tunneling in saturated ground, no matter how short the excavation time is, consolidation involves dissipation of pore pressure according to diffusion law. This time-dependent process, however, is not represented in their “steady-state” LDP equations. According to Eqs. (11) and (12), the variation of normalized displacement ($u_r/u_{r,max}$) is only affected by the normalized distance to tunnel face (x/D), the constant value of normalized displacement at the face ($u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$) and the constant value of the ratio p_o/σ'_{vo} . Thus, the steady-state LDP equations would not suffice for predicting the transient radial displacement of consolidating ground resulting from a step-wise coupled simulation. This limitation raises the second question addressed in this paper: How can LDP equations be improved to account for transient H-M response in saturated tunnels?

1.3. Aim of the study

The aim of this paper is to answer the above two questions by completing the following two tasks. First, the transient H-M response (i.e., the pore pressure and deformation behaviors) of the ground surrounding a deep advancing tunnel is investigated. The tunnel is represented by a 2-D axisymmetric coupled model and subjected to an isotropic in situ stress field. The tunnel is then excavated in a step-wise coupled manner so that the undrained and drained loadings during excavation can be properly applied. Second, by considering the transient coupling effect, nonlinear unloading factors for excavation pore pressure in CCM will be proposed. These factors will account for the non-monotonic behavior of pore pressure change induced during the tunnel face advance. A new set transient LDP equations capable of predicting transient radial displacements will also be proposed. This new equation will include time-dependent constants that represent the transient nature of the consolidating ground.

2. Axisymmetric model and excavation procedure

An axisymmetric coupled model of the advancing tunnel is created in the computer program Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua (FLAC) developed by Itasca (2011a). FLAC is a 2-D explicit finite difference program that is commonly used in various geotechnical engineering applications to study the mechanical behavior of continuous medium as it reaches equilibrium or

steady plastic flow. The program has a capability of performing groundwater flow calculation with solid interaction within the framework of the quasi-static Biot's theory of poroelasticity (Biot, 1941). Starting from a state of mechanical equilibrium, the fully coupled H-M simulation in FLAC involves a series of steps. Each step includes one or more flow steps (flow loop) to evaluate the increased pore pressure, followed by enough mechanical steps (mechanical loop) to evaluate the contribution of the volumetric strain. The total stress correction due to pore pressure arising from fluid flow and from the mechanical volume strain is then used to evaluate the effective stress and detect ground failure (Itasca, 2011b).

The advancing tunnel is represented by a 2-D axisymmetric model of an unlined circular excavation of radius $R = 2.5$ m and at a depth of $H = 225$ m through an elastic and saturated medium subjected to total isotropic in situ stress of $\sigma_o = 4.50$ MPa and initial hydrostatic pore pressure of $p_o = 2.25$ MPa. Tunnel at this depth has been reported by Graziani and Boldini (2012) when investigating the influence of H-M coupling on deep tunnel response in clays. As will be seen later, the results of the numerical modeling in this paper are also normalized, and thus, they should be applicable to other tunnel depths as well.

The paper adopts the sign convention used in rock mechanics that stress and displacement are positive for compression. The ground properties are given in Table 1, while the layout of the tunnel model and the corresponding boundary conditions are shown in Fig. 5a. The model boundaries are impermeable, except those at the tunnel wall and face. An axisymmetric model with a circular boundary and isotropic stress is an appropriate approximation for very deep tunnels where the half-space conditions corresponding to the ground surface can be disregarded.

Tunnel advance is simulated by progressively deactivating 40 excavation regions of width $\Delta x = 1.25$ m from $x/D = 10$ to $x/D = 0$ over an excavation period of 10 days, implying the excavation rate of $v_a = 5$ m/day (Fig. 5b). As shown in Callari (2004), $v_a = 5$ m/day has been observed to give the best match of vertical displacement between 2-D simulation of an advancing tunnel using the CCM approach and 3-D simulation. Callari (2004) has also reported that using a very low advance rate ($v_a \ll 5$ m/day) will cause considerable coupling effects in the form of negative excess pore pressures as a consequence of the solid skeleton dilatancy. On the other hand, using a very high advance rate ($v_a \gg 5$ m/day) will cause the pore pressure near the tunnel to reach

the steady state as soon as the final drainage boundary conditions are attained. Thus, for these practical reasons, $v_a = 5$ m/day is selected for the simulation.

During deactivation of each region, the face is instantaneously removed for a period of $\Delta t = 0$ (undrained loading), followed by drained consolidation for a period of $\Delta t = \Delta x/v_a$ (drained loading). These alternating stages of undrained excavation and drained consolidation are continued until the final tunnel face at $x/D = 0$ is reached at the excavation time of $t = 10$ days. In this state, the response of the ground surrounding the tunnel is called the short-term response, representing the H-M response that is induced immediately after the excavation of the final face. This state also corresponds to the start of the standstill period, marked as the normalized consolidation time of $t^* = 0$, where $t^* = R^2/c_v$ (Giraud and Rousset, 1996; Li, 1999). The consolidation coefficient c_v is calculated as $c_v = k_H/(\gamma_w \cdot S)$, where k_H is the ground conductivity, γ_w is the unit weight of water, and S is the storativity defined as $S = n/K_w + 1/(K + 4G/3)$, where n is the porosity, K_w is the bulk modulus of water, and K and G are the bulk and shear moduli of the ground, respectively. The consolidation is then continued towards the total standstill period of $t = 930$ days ($t^* = 100$) until the long-term H-M response of the ground is in steady-state condition.

3. Transient H-M response of an advancing tunnel

During the excavation period, the transient H-M response is monitored at $x/D = 5$ (see the top inset in Fig. 6). Unless stated otherwise, all pore pressures are total (initial hydrostatic plus excess pore pressure) and all stresses are effective. In terms of pore pressure behavior, monitored at 1 m above the tunnel wall, the excess pore pressure develops long before the tunnel face arrives at the monitoring point (Fig. 6a). The pore pressure starts to deviate from the in situ value of 2.25 MPa at $t = 3$ days ($x/D = 7$), steeply reaches the peak value of 2.65 MPa at $t = 4.25$ days ($x/D = 5.75$), and drops to 1.75 MPa by the time the tunnel face arrives at the monitoring point at $t = 5$ days ($x/D = 5$). The pore pressure continues to fall sharply as the tunnel face passes the monitoring point before it starts to decrease more steadily at $t = 6$ days ($x/D = 4$). The discontinuous and non-smooth shapes of the H-M response shown in Fig. 6 are due to the transient response from the alternating undrained and drained loadings.

Similar behavior is observed for the convergence behavior in Fig. 6b. The convergence starts to deviate from 0 cm at $t = 3$ days ($x/D = 7$) and quickly increases to 3.0 cm when the tunnel

face arrives at the monitoring point at $t = 5$ days ($x/D = 5$). The convergence keeps increasing as the face advances before it starts to flatten out toward a constant value of 4.2 cm at $t = 7$ days ($x/D = 3$). For the effective stresses behavior (Fig. 6c), the starting point to deviate from the in situ value of 2.25 MPa is at $t = 3$ days ($x/D = 7$), and the ending point to remain constant at $\sigma'_\theta = 4.65$ MPa and $\sigma'_r = 1.25$ MPa is at $t = 7$ days ($x/D = 3$).

The significance of the results presented in Fig. 6 is threefold. First, when a tunnel face is being excavated, the induced pore pressure and deformation behavior in the vicinity of the face are neither the initial nor the final response. It is rather the transient response because the induced H-M response has already started long before the tunnel face arrives at the face and ends after it passes the face. Second, the pore pressure behavior is not linearly dissipated with the excavation time, hence with the distance to the tunnel face. In fact, due to the transient coupling effect, the induced pore pressure in the ground ahead of the face increases above the in situ value before the face arrives. This non-monotonic behavior and increase of pore pressure above the initial hydrostatic value is analogous to the Mandel-Cryer effect (Abousleiman et al., 1996; Cryer, 1963; Mandel, 1953; Gutierrez and Lewis, 2002). In tunneling, the Mandel-Cryer effect has been seen to occur at the tunnel crown and is caused by the stress concentration in the stiffer zone that is still undrained (Prasetyo and Gutierrez, 2016a, 2016b). This non-monotonic behavior leads to a proposition to modify the assumed linearity of the unloading factor for excavation pore pressure in CCM. Third, it is envisioned that during the standstill period, the H-M response of the unexcavated ground ahead of the face (called the advanced core) will behave in an equivalent manner to that at the monitored point. That is, after the final face is reached, the ground would continue to converge due to the dissipation of pore pressure in the advanced core. This hypothesis leads to another proposition to develop a new LDP equation capable of capturing the transient radial displacements during the standstill period, considering the time-dependent nature of the consolidating ground. These propositions are presented in the following sections.

4. Proposition 1: Nonlinear unloading factor for excavation pore pressure in CCM

As shown in Fig. 6a, there are two vital locations during the excavation period that are needed for modifying the linearity of the unloading factor for excavation pore pressure. The first location is the starting point x_o , where the pore pressure and displacement start to deviate from

their in situ values as the tunnel face is approaching the monitoring point. The second location is the final point x_f , where the responses become independent of the face advance as the tunnel face is leaving the monitoring point. If $x/D = 5$ in Fig. 6 is considered as the reference point ($x = 0$), then it is found that for pore pressure, $x_o = 2D$ and $x_f = -D$, while for displacement, $x_o = 2D$ and $x_f = -2D$. Consequently, the excavation time intervals can be defined as

$$t_\lambda = \frac{x_o - x_f}{v_a} = \frac{2D - (-2D)}{v_a} = \frac{4D}{v_a} \text{ day for excavation force, and} \quad (13)$$

$$t_\alpha = \frac{x_o - x_f}{v_a} = \frac{2D - (-D)}{v_a} = \frac{3D}{v_a} \text{ day for excavation pore pressure} \quad (14)$$

To obtain the unloading factor for excavation force $\lambda(t)$, a piece-wise linear combination is made for the curve u_r versus x/D (Fig. 7a) and the curve u_r versus λ (Fig. 7b). From this combination, the curve $\lambda(t)$ versus x/D can be generated. Using Eq. (13), the corresponding time interval t_λ for every point in the curve $\lambda(t)$ versus x/D can then be obtained. The same steps to get the curve $\lambda(t)$ versus x/D are then repeated to get the unloading factor for excavation pore pressure $\alpha(t)$ versus x/D using Eq. (14). Having performed this operation, the desired unloading factors for excavation force and pore pressure considering the transient coupling effect are shown in Fig. 8. These piece-wise combinations of $\lambda(t)$ and $\alpha(t)$ versus x/D along with the corresponding t_λ and t_α are presented in Table 2.

An interesting result that is worth mentioning from Fig. 8 and Table 2 is the expected nonlinearity of the curve $\alpha(t)$ versus x/D and the corresponding negative values of $\alpha(t)$. By substituting these values in Eq. (2), the excavation pore pressure $\bar{p}(t)$ will be larger than 1. Consequently, the applied pore pressure on the tunnel boundary will be larger than the in situ value, which corresponds to the observed Mandel-Cryer effect in the pore pressure behavior in Fig. 6a. This non-monotonic behavior of pore pressure was not considered in the so-called extended CCM for tunneling in saturated ground proposed by Callari (2004), and Callari and Casini (2005). Instead, a linear relationship was adopted for $\alpha(t)$ versus x/D which, based on the results in this paper, would oversimplify the coupling effect induced by the advancing tunnel. Thus, it is envisioned that by using the transient unloading factors $\lambda(t)$ and $\alpha(t)$ from this study (Table 2) into Eqs. (1) and (2), the 3-D effect of the tunnel face advance in deep saturated ground

will be more properly represented in an equivalent 2-D plane strain model than in one that uses the assumed linear behavior.

5. Proposition 2: Transient LDP equations

The results in Section 3 explicitly shows that LDP equations considering the transient coupling effect will be essential. The equation should involve time-dependent constants that represent the transient nature of the consolidating ground. To do this, the radial displacements occurring during the standstill period are collected and their normalized values $u_r/u_{r,max}$ are plotted against the distance from the tunnel face x/D at various normalized consolidation times t^* . Because it has been difficult to fit the simulation data into a typical single sigmoid curve, the typical S-shape of LDP is divided into two parts. The first part defines radial displacements located ahead of the face ($x/D < 0$), while the second part defines those located behind the face ($x/D \geq 0$).

For the region ahead of the face ($x/D < 0$), the following equation is proposed:

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = \frac{u_{ro}}{u_{r,max}} \exp\left(2.11 \frac{x}{D}\right) + 0.2 \exp\left(\frac{x}{5D}\right) (1 - \exp(-A)) \quad (15)$$

For the region behind the face ($x/D \geq 0$), the following equation is proposed:

$$\frac{u_r}{u_{r,max}} = \frac{u_{ro}}{u_{r,max}} + \left(1 - \frac{u_{ro}}{u_{r,max}}\right) \left(1 - \left(\frac{B}{B + x/D}\right)^2\right) \quad (16)$$

where A and B are the time-dependent constants considering the transient coupling effect during the consolidation. Eqs. (15) and (16) are transient time-dependent extensions of the LDP equations proposed by Nam and Bobet (2007), and Unlu and Gercek (2003), respectively.

The constants $u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$, A and B that will fit Eqs. (15) and (16) at various t^* are shown in Table 3. It can be seen that the transient coupling effect is represented by the evolution of deformation $u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$ (mechanical response) with respect to the diffusivity of the ground t^* (hydraulic response). To see the suitability of these constants with the new LDP equation, the normalized transient $u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$ at $t^* = 1$ and 100 are plotted in Fig. 9. As expected, the transient LDPs fit the simulation data accurately. With the increase of consolidation time, the simulation data show a reduction in the downward concavity for the region ahead of the face, as well as a reduction in the upward concavity for the region behind the face.

For practical implementation of the new LDP equations, the relationships among the constants A , B and $u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$ with consolidation time need to be established through curve fitting. The relationship between $u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$ and t^* needs to be found first. The constants A and B can be implicitly correlated to t^* through the curves $u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$ versus A and $u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$ versus B , respectively. To find $u_{r,max}$, the relationship between tunnel strain $u_{r,max}/R$ and t^* will also be needed. The following equations have been found to curve fit the correlation among these constants.

$$\text{For } u_{ro}/u_{r,max} \text{ versus } t^*: \quad \frac{u_{ro}}{u_{r,max}} = 0.28 + 0.028 \left[1 - \exp(-0.56 \log t^*) \right] \quad (17)$$

$$\text{For } u_{ro}/u_{r,max} \text{ versus } A: \quad A = -\frac{1}{2.4} \ln \left[-\frac{u_{ro}/u_{r,max} - 0.305}{0.028} \right] \quad (18)$$

$$\text{For } u_{ro}/u_{r,max} \text{ versus } B: \quad B = 0.85 - 2.10^5 \exp \left[-47 u_{ro}/u_{r,max} \right] \quad (19)$$

$$\text{For } u_{r,max}/R \text{ versus } t^*: \quad \frac{u_{r,max}}{R} = 2.0 - 0.3 \exp \left[-0.005 t^* \right] \quad (20)$$

As can be seen from Fig. 10, the relationships defined in Eqs. (17)–(20) fit the simulation data very well with R^2 values that are very close to 1.0.

To construct the transient LDPs at various consolidation times, the constants $u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$, A and B are recalculated at various t^* using Eqs. (17)–(19). The resulting constants are then used in Eqs. (15) and (16) to obtain the normalized radial displacement $u_r/u_{r,max}$. To calculate the actual values of radial displacement u_r , Eq. (20) can then be used.

Fig. 11 plots the resulting transient LDPs with varying consolidation times from $t = 5$ days to $t = 930$ days. The steady-state LDPs from Nam and Bobet (2007) are also shown for comparison. As expected, the new transient LDPs fit the simulation data more closely than the steady-state ones. As the consolidation time increases, the transient LDPs can follow the expected changes in the concavity of the displacement profile along the tunnel axis, capturing the transient coupling effect during the consolidation (see explanation for Fig. 9). On the other hand, the steady-state LDPs only agree well with the simulation data at $x/D \geq 5$. In particular, the steady-state LDPs cannot follow the concavity of the displacement profiles for those behind the face at $0 \leq x/D < 5$ and for those ahead of the face at $x/D \leq 0$. Even though the difference in the radial displacement between the transient and steady-state LDPs is not large at a large distance behind the face, the

difference in the radial displacement around and behind the face can be significant. For example, at $t = 5$ days, the difference in the radial displacement between the two LDPs at $x/D = -0.5$ is almost 0.5 cm. At this location, the simulation data, transient LDP, and steady-state LDP give $u_r = 0.44, 0.45,$ and 0.90 cm, respectively. From this result, it is evident that the transient LDP is able to predict the correct behavior of tunnel convergence ahead of the face, which would be useful to help determine the face stabilization method to control its magnitude. As pointed out by Lunardi (2008), the ability to control the deformation ahead of the face is the key to control the deformation behind the face.

In general, as shown in Fig. 11, the steady-state LDPs overestimate the magnitude of radial displacements for $x/D \geq 5$. This difference is somehow expected as the steady-state LDP equations were developed through a series of uncoupled simulations in which the tunnel model was geomechanically equilibrated under the steady-state pore pressure distribution instead of under the transient one (i.e., as the one performed in this paper). Hence, dissipation of pore pressure due to the time-dependent process is not represented in the steady-state LDP. As mentioned earlier in Section 1.2, the radial displacement in the steady-state LDP equations is only affected by the normalized distance to tunnel face (x/D), the constant value of normalized displacement at the face ($u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$) and the constant value of the ratio p_o/σ'_{vo} .

Therefore, result in Fig. 11 reveals the validity of not only the proposed LDP equations, but also the equations defining the time-dependent constants $u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$, A , B and $u_{r,max}/R$. Despite a limited number of coupled simulations, this result validates the hypothesis that the LDP equations must be related to time-dependent constants capturing the transient nature of radial displacements of the consolidating ground. In tunnel engineering, the correct prediction of the transient deformation behavior is vital because knowing when the tunnel deformation will reach a certain magnitude helps determine the timing for the support installation. It is for that purpose the transient LDP equations are developed. The equations may serve as a first approach to estimate the magnitude of radial displacement of tunneling in saturated ground.

6. Conclusions

The effect of transient H-M interaction on CCM and LDP of an advancing tunnel in deep saturated ground was studied. The tunnel was built in a 2-D axisymmetric model and its

advancement was simulated through a step-wise excavation procedure featuring alternating undrained and drained loadings. Having observed that the H-M response was transiently induced by the excavation and that the induced pore pressure response was not linearly dissipated with excavation time, this study suggested two propositions.

First, this study proposed using the new nonlinear unloading factors for excavation pore pressure in CCM. The new unloading factors have negative values that would make the excavation pore pressure on the tunnel boundary higher than the in situ value, which corresponds to the observed Mandel-Cryer effect during the excavation. It is envisioned that the 3-D effect of an advancing tunnel would be more properly represented in the 2-D plane strain model that uses the nonlinear unloading factors than in the model that uses the linear ones.

Second, this study proposed using the new transient LDP equations for expressing radial displacements along the axis of the tunnel in saturated ground. The equations consider the transient coupling effect that is induced by the consolidation process. At various consolidation times, the transient LDPs fit the radial displacements more accurately than the steady-state ones. Knowing the correct behavior of tunnel convergence ahead of the face would be useful to help determine the face stabilization method to control its magnitude. Similarly, knowing when the tunnel deformation behind the face will reach a certain magnitude may help determine the timing for the support installation. It is for that purpose the transient LDP equations are developed. The equations may serve as a first approach to estimate the magnitude of radial displacement of tunneling in saturated ground.

Despite the limited number of simulations, the new LDP equations may offer a new route to capturing the transient nature of displacement of deep tunnels in saturated ground. In addition, the paper may also set a framework to develop transient LDPs for more complex ground behaviors.

The resulting relationships from the two propositions are normalized, and thus, they should be applicable to other tunnel depths as well.

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Table 1 Ground properties for advancing tunnel problem.

Ground properties	Value
Hydraulic conductivity, k_H (m/s)	$5.0 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Porosity, ϕ	0.39
Shear modulus, G (Pa)	$1.3 \cdot 10^8$
Drained bulk modulus, K (Pa)	$1.3 \cdot 10^8$
Fluid bulk modulus, K_w (Pa)	$2.0 \cdot 10^9$

Table 2 Transient unloading factors for the excavation force λ and pore pressure α .

Force			Pore pressure		
$\lambda(t)$	x/D	t_λ (day)	$\alpha(t)$	x/D	t_α (day)
0.00	2.00	0.00	0.00	2.00	0.00
0.01	1.50	0.50	-0.05	1.50	0.50
0.03	1.00	1.00	-0.25	1.00	1.00
0.13	0.50	1.50	-0.40	0.71	1.29
0.31	0.25	1.75	-0.23	0.50	1.50
0.70	0.00	2.00	0.31	0.25	1.75
0.83	-0.50	2.50	0.52	0.00	2.00
0.95	-1.00	3.00	0.87	-0.50	2.50
0.98	-1.50	3.50	0.93	-0.75	2.75
1.00	-2.00	4.00	1.00	-1.00	3.00

Table 3 Time-dependent constants from the simulation to construct the transient LDPs based on Eqs. (15) and (16).

t^* (day)	$u_{ro}/u_{r,max}$	A	B	$u_{r,max}/R$ (%)
1 (5)	0.281	0.050	0.482	1.687
5 (30)	0.289	0.220	0.606	1.697
10 (80)	0.292	0.316	0.636	1.703
20 (180)	0.295	0.408	0.651	1.712
50 (425)	0.296	0.520	0.676	1.720
100 (920)	0.300	0.711	0.708	1.758